

Aurone glycosides from *Pterocarpus santalinus*

Janhavi Singh

Department of Chemistry, U. P. College, Varanasi-221002, India

Manuscript received 2 September 2002, accepted 12 December 2002

The heart-wood of *Pterocarpus santalinus* (Family : Papilionaceae) has been found to contain two aurone glycosides, characterized as 6-hydroxy-1-methyl-3',4',5'-trimethoxyaurone-4-*O*-rhamnoside and 6,4'-dihydroxyaurone-4-*O*-neohesperidoside.

Species of *Pterocarpus* are distributed around Gorakhpur, Bundelkhand, South India, Srilanka, and are known to be rich in isoflavonoids and terpenoids¹.

We report here the isolation of compounds **1** and **2** from the ethanolic extract of the heart-wood of the plant *Pterocarpus santalinus*.

Compound 1 :

Compound **1** was found to be glycosidic in nature and on hydrolysis gave an aglycone and a sugar. The sugar moiety was identified as rhamnose on the basis of co-TLC with authentic sample and spectral studies. The aglycone was found to be aurone on the basis of UV spectral data². ¹H NMR study of the aglycone showed presence of three aromatic protons. A multiplet at δ 7.88–8.00 (2H) was assigned to H-2' and -6' protons. The presence of three OCH₃ groups was confirmed by a singlet at δ 3.65 (9H). The signal at δ 1.68 (3H, s) was assigned to CH₃ and that at δ 6.72 (1H, s) for benzyl proton (=CH). A singlet at δ 6.23 (1H, H-5) revealed the presence of trisubstituted A-ring. The aglycone on acetylation formed a diacetate indicating the presence of two hydroxyl groups. The position of attachment of hydroxyl group and sugar moiety was confirmed by the comparison of UV-spectra of aglycone and glycoside. The position of one of the hydroxyl groups at C-6 was confirmed by UV-shift³. The position of methyl groups at C-7 was confirmed by ¹H NMR data. The sugar moiety was attached at C-4 position of A-ring. The EI-mass spectrum of the compound showed the molecular ion peak at m/z 520 [M]⁺ and two mass fragments at m/z 192 and 166 were due to the presence of A and B moiety. On the basis of chemical, and spectroscopic studies the structure of compound **1** was established as 6-hydroxy-7-methyl-3',4', 5'-trimethoxyaurone-4-*O*-rhamnopyranoside.

Compound 2 :

Compound **2** on hydrolysis gave an aglycone and sugars glucose and rhamnose. Methylated compound on hydroly-

sis gave 4-hydroxy-6,4'-dimethoxyaurone showing that the bioside was linked at position-4 of the aglycone. The nature of intersugar linkage was deduced by comparison of the rhamnose methyl signal with the corresponding signals of rutinose (δ 0.08–0.95, br) and neohesperidoside (δ 1.20–1.35, d) to be of neohesperidoside type⁵.

Aglycone was found to be aurone in nature on the basis of characteristic colour reactions and UV absorptions [3]. ¹H NMR study of the aglycone showed the presence of six aromatic protons. A multiplet at δ 7.7–7.9 (2H) was assigned to H-2' and H-6' and a singlet at δ 6.9 (2H) to H-3' and H-5' protons. A doublet at δ 6.3 (J 2 Hz) was attributed to H-5 and a doublet at δ 6.5 (J 2 Hz) for H-7. A singlet at δ 6.65 was assigned to benzylic proton (=CH-).

Aglycone on acetylation gave a triacetate indicating the presence of three hydroxyls. The position of hydroxyls was confirmed by UV shift and mass fragmentation pattern. Two mass fragments at m/z 118 and 152 showed the presence of two hydroxyl groups in the A-ring and one in B-ring. Attachment of sugar moiety at position C-4 was confirmed by UV shift.

Structure of the aglycone was further confirmed by chemical degradation method. Trimethyl ether of aglycone in dioxan was treated with aq. NaOH (8%), triethylbenzylammonium chloride (TEBA) and H₂O₂ (25%) at room temperature when the aurone was chemically degraded. A mixture of two products was obtained, both being acidic in nature and identified as 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxybenzoic acid and anisic acid, respectively. This chemical degradation method showed the presence of two hydroxyl groups in the A-ring and one in the B-ring of aglycone.

On the basis of these evidences structure of compound **2** is assigned as 6,4'-dihydroxyaurone 4-*O*-neohesperidoside. These glycoside **1** and **2** have not been reported earlier.

Experimental

The wood (4 kg) was extracted in boiling ethanol. The concentrated ethanolic extract was poured into ice-cold water when a coloured residue (Fraction I) and an aqueous solution (Fraction II) were obtained.

Fraction I : It was successively extracted with petrol, benzene and ethyl acetate respectively in a soxhlet.

Ethyl acetate fraction contained a single compound **1** (single spot on silica gel TLC plate, R_f 0.34, B : A : W - 4 : 1 : 5, spray iodine vapour, crystallized from EtOAc-petrol (3 : 1, v/v), m.p. 182° (Found : C, 57.58; H, 5.42. $C_{25}H_{28}O_{12}$ calcd. for : C, 57.61; H, 5.38%); λ_{max} (MeOH) 260, 270, 296, 330, 405; +NaOMe 262, 280, 338, 400, 468; +NaOAc 263, 284, 398, 470 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3410, 1635, 720, 670 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$, 250 MHz) 1.2 (3H, d, rhamnose methyl), 1.68 (1H, s, CH_3), 3.5–3.8 (4H, br, sugar protons), 3.65 (9H, s, OCH_3), 4.2 (1H, s, H-1''), 6.23 (1H, s, H-5), 6.72 (1H, s, =CH-), 7.88–8.00 (2H, s, H-2' and -6').

An ethanolic solution of **1** was refluxed with 7% H_2SO_4 for 3 h and then poured in ice-cold water. The yellow solid that separated out was crystallized from EtOAc : petrol-ether (3 : 7, v/v) (Found : C, 63.46; H, 5.15. $C_{19}C_7H_{18}$ calcd. for : C, 63.6; H, 5.03%); δ ($CDCl_3$, 250 MHz) 1.49 (1H, s, CH_3), 3.63 (9H, s, OCH_3), 6.23 (1H, s, H-5), 6.75 (1H, s, =CH-), 7.88–8.00 (2H, m, H-2' and -6'); MS (70 eV) m/z 520 (M^+), 358, 192, 166, 138.

The benzene fraction was chromatographed over silica gel and eluted successively with hexane, benzene and ethyl acetate. EtOAc : C_6H_6 (8 : 2) eluate (single spot on silica gel TLC plate, R_f 0.38, BAW, iodine vapour) gave a yellow

coloured compound **2** (600 mg), crystallized from EtOAc : petrol (1 : 5, v/v), m.p. 224° (Found : C, 56.20; H, 4.85. $C_{27}H_{30}O_{14}$ calcd. for : C, 56.05; H, 5.10%); λ_{max} (MeOH), 251, 268, 325, 398; +NaOMe 253, 270, 321, 451; +NaOAc 252, 272, 325, 453 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3370, 1631, 730, 680 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$, 250 MHz) 1.3 (3H, d, rhamnose methyl), 3.50–3.85 (10H, m, sugar protons), 4.9–5.1 (1H, s, H-1' rhamnosyl), 5.27 (1H, m, H-1'' glucosyl), 6.3 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-5), 6.5 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-7), 6.65 (1H, s, =CH-) 6.9 (2H, s, H-3' and -5'), 7.7–7.9 (2H, H-2' and -6').

On acid hydrolysis, **2** gave an aglycone identified as 4, 6,4'-trihydroxyaurone, m.p. 295°, identified by spectral data (UV, IR, NMR, MS). Chromatography (PC) of the aqueous layer in BuOH-AcOH- H_2O (4 : 1 : 5, v/v) showed glucose and rhamnose (R_f 0.18, 0.34, respectively).

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to C.D.R.I., C.I.M.A.P., Lucknow, India, for spectra assistance.

References

1. T. R. Seshadri, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, **11**, 881; J. Mitra and T. Josh. *Phytochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 2328.
2. T. A. Geissman, "The Chemistry of Flavonoid Compounds," Pergamon, New York, 1962.
3. S. Asen and J. R. Plimma, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, **11**, 2601.
4. M. C. D. Nascimento, R. L. D. Dias, and W. B. Mors, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, **15**, 1553.
5. J. P. Kutney, W. D. C. Warnock and B. Gilbert, *Phytochemistry*, 1970, **9**, 1877; R. T. Sherwood, M. Shamma and J. L. Moniot, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, **12**, 2275.